

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series
Vol.XVI.Book.I-IV

January - December 2024

किरणावली
Sanskrit Research Foundation
Thiruvananthapuram

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series

Vol.XVI. Book. I-IV

January-December

2024

Sanskrit Research Foundation

T.C 39/37

Thiruvananthapuram-36

KIRANĀVALĪ

ISSN 0975-4067

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14576256>

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

A Peer-Reviewed Research Journal

Editor

Prof. Dr.M. Manimohan (Rtd)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.m.manimohan@gmail.com

Executive Editor

Prof. Dr.C.S.Sasikumar (Rtd.)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.sasikumarcs@gmail.com

Managing Editor

Prof. Dr.G.Narayanan

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.g.narayanan@gmail.com

Editorial board

Dr.V.Sisupalapanikkar, Professor of Sanskrit(Rtd.) Uty. of Kerala

Dr.K.Muthulakshmi, Professor of Vedanta, S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.R.Vijayakumar, Professor of Vyakarana(Rtd.), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.P.Chithambaran, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd),S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.P.K.Dharmarajan, Professor of Sahitya, (Rtd) S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.K.K.Sundaresan, Associate Professor in Vedanta, SSUS.Kalady

Dr.S.Sobhana, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.T.Devarajan, Professor of Sanskrit (Rtd), University of Kerala

Associate Editor

Dr.R.Jinu

Associate Professor, Dept of English,

Noorul Islam Centre For Higher Education, Kumaracoil,

Thuckalay, Kanyakumari, Tamil Nadu

jichelnu@gmail.com

Contents

Editors Note	5
Fractions or kalāsavarṇa - Concepts in the Gaṇitasārasaṅgraha (G.S.S) of Mahāvira	Dr. P.M.Mini 7
Vrikshayurveda Literature- A Review	Dr. K.Murali 12
Existence Of Mind and its Function: Śrī Śankara's Perspective	Dr. V Vasanthakumari 23
Regional Peculiarities in Prakriyāsarvasva	Dr. Yamuna.K 30
Parāstotra - Edition and Study	Dr. J.P. Prajith 37
Alienation through Exile: A Critical Introspection into John Dos Passos' Nineteen Nineteen	Dr. Sanil T. Sunny 44
The Evolution of Indian Sculptural Art: Interaction with Western Styles and Development of Modernism	Dr. T.G Jyothilal 49
Scope of Sanskrit Studies in the Kerala Context	Dr.Shylaja S 55
Desamangalam Srikantha Variar - A Versatile Scholar	Dr.V.P.Udayakumar 67
A Comprehensive Review of Adharaneeya and Dharaneeya Vega	Dr. H.A.Anu, Dr. Haritha Chandran, Dr. Haroon Irshad, Dr. Leena P.Nair 72
A Significant Emphasis on Charakokta Chaturvidha Pariksha	Dr.Kesavan.V G, Dr.Haroon Irshad, Dr.Leena P.Nair, Dr. Haritha Chandran 84
Concept Of Manas- A Glimpse from Yoga Darsana	Dr. Anu Gopal, Dr. Haritha Chandran, Dr. Leena P Nair, Dr. Haroon Irshad 96
Women Life in Royal Harem- A Study Based on Nāṭyaśāstra And Mālavikāgnimitra	Dr. Ajitha T S 106
Effective Strategies For Implementing The Integrated Teacher Education Programme Under NEP- 2020	Prof. K.K. Harshkumar, Dr. Anand Rautmale 113
“Pancha Mahabhuta in Ayurveda: Understanding and Practical Applications”	Dr. Aswiny Sreekumar.T 121
“Dynamic Portrayals of Women in Amarushatak: Unravelling Love, Creation, Destruction, Submission, and Dominance”	Dr. Preeti R. Pujara 135
Literary Representation of the Ashtamudi Lake sketched through Poetic Imagery: An Exploration based on Selected Poems in Malayalam	Jayalekshmi J 145
Reviving Classical Narratives: Exploring the Cultural, Linguistic, and Literary Significance of Sanskrit Literature in Contemporary Contexts	Dr. Yeshpal, 155
Vedic Thought on Nakshatra Science	Dr. Kanta 172
Vedāntic Reflections in Kālidāsa's Literature: A Journey through Ancient Wisdom	Dr. K. K. Abdul Majeed 179
The Transformative Power of Yogic Meditation: Insights from the Isha Upanishad	Dev Prakash Gujela , Neha Gujela 188
Sanskrit: The Language of Innovation in Ancient Indian Knowledge Systems.	Abdul Rasheed K. 197
The Role of Vedānta as a Mediator between Science and Religion	Dr. Abdulla Sha R., Dr. Midhun P., 207

Concept of Guṇa in Bhagavad Gīta	Dr. Shyji K.K.	212
Pancatantram's perspective of accepting an 'hors de combat'. Kasthuri P. K.		217
Integral Yoga of Sri Aurobindo	Remya.S	223
The Historical Aspects Of 'Translation' (Anuvādam) - An Overview	Dr. Sajeesh C S	227
The Malayali Diaspora in the US: A close reading of Mira Jacob	Nirupama Suneetha	235
From Elancon To Kollam: The Transformation of A Port Cty	Gowri S Panicker	242
Influence of Nārayanīya on Kṛṣṇagīti	Dr Jayanisha K	255
Subverting Ableist Binaries: An Analysis of the Confluence of Disability Studies and Blue Humanities in Toni Crowther's From Wheelchair to Water	Sneha Jacob	263
Connecting the Concept of 'Avatar' to the Concept of Consciousness in Upanishads	Venugopalan P.M	269
Extraction of historicity from Sanskrit literature	Soorya A.P	281
चिन्सुखेन प्रतिपादितं अविद्यालक्षणम्	डॉ. सन्तोष सि. आर्	285
सामाजिकसमस्यापरिहारे भरतीयज्ञानपरम्परान्तर्गतस्य योगशास्त्रस्य स्थानम्	डा. श्रीजित् टि.जि	289
पतञ्जलिकालीनः लोकव्यवहारः-महाभाष्याधारेण एकमनुशीलनम्	डा.रूपा. वि	293
मानवीयमूल्यबोधोत्तरणे मूच्छकटिकम्	ड.मृत्युञ्जयमण्डलः परेशकैवर्त्यः	299
रघुवंशमहाकाव्ये रसतत्त्वसमीक्षणम्	काञ्चनवारिकः	304
नारीचैतन्योद्बोधे शङ्खनादः	डॉ टुम्पा जाना	308
आधुनिकसंस्कृतसाहित्ये गलज्जलिकायाः वैशिष्ट्यम्	सतीश चन्द्र दास	313
श्रीमच्छंकराचार्यकृतच्छान्दोग्योपनिषद्भाष्यस्य कतिपयशब्दवाक्यानां रूपवाक्यशब्दार्थतत्त्वनिरूपणम्	रणिता घोष	321
सदाचारो वेदाश्च ।	डा.अशोक कुमार एन्.के.	327
साम्प्रतिकसन्दर्भे अपरिग्रहः	डॉ. शुभमयपाहाडी	331
मनुसंहिता : 'ब्रह्मतत्त्व' विषयकम् एकं संक्षिप्तं मतम्	अमल कुमार कर	335
श्रीकाशीमठाधीशानां श्रीमत्सुधीन्द्रतीर्थानां स्तोत्रेषु छन्दांसि तथा सौन्दर्यम्	दिव्यश्री जगदीश पै बि. , & भास्कर वि भट्टः	339
सिद्धान्तग्रन्थेषु ब्राह्मणमानम्	डा. राघवेन्द्रः	347
एतत्संज्ञेत्यत्र कः समासः	डा. गोपालकृष्णन् रघुः	352
मेघदूतस्य सांस्कृतिकमीमांसा	डा. सत्येन्दु शर्मा	356
जान्-म्यूर-प्रणीतस्य 'श्रीपौलचरित्रम्' इति महाकाव्यस्य संस्कृतालङ्कारशास्त्रदृष्ट्या समीक्षामिका विमृष्टिः	डा. सौम्यजित् सेनः	360
आधुनिकयुगे संस्कृतशिक्षा प्रसारार्थं विद्यासागरस्यावदानम्	डः तानिया-सिकदारः	369
तद्धितप्रत्ययेषु इत्संज्ञकवर्णाः ।	आतिरा. जि	372
अद्वैतसिद्धेः मङ्गलश्लोकस्य अप्रामाण्यशङ्कावारणम्	कार्तिक शर्मा के , ड. हरिकृष्ण शर्मा के.एन्	376
न्यायव्याकरणतन्त्रानुसंधे पदस्वरूपविवेचनम्	प्रणबेष् भट्टाचार्यः	381
पीयूषवर्षश्रीजयदेवाचार्य-श्रीकेशविमिश्रयोः मते शान्तरसविमर्शः	सत्येनशीटः	387
आलंकारिकदण्डिस्वीकृतः शब्दालङ्कारप्रपञ्चः	डॉ. शुभ्रजित् सेनः	393
लिधा एव पदशब्दस्य प्रवृत्तिः	डा. सुदीप-मण्डलः	400
About the journal		407

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14646554>

Literary Representation of the Ashtamudi Lake sketched through Poetic Imagery: An Exploration based on Selected Poems in Malayalam

Jayalekshmi J¹

Abstract

Ashtamudi, with its flora and fauna is showcased as an enriched cultural landscape and as a recurring poetic image in literature, paintings and films. Ashtamudi lake often foregrounds as a character and a strong motif in representing the flow of life and fertility in literature, where Kollam is set as milieu. Literature of Kollam often delineates how water sources, especially Ashtamudi lake becomes a cultural landscape in the representation of human life. This paper analyzes the literary representation of Ashtamudi lake through vivid lacustrine poetic images in the portrayal of the life of the natives, and as a cultural landscape, as a means of living, as a backdrop for evoking emotions like love, sexuality, poetic and artistic creativity, entertainment, and how it satiates the visual, auditory, olfactory, tactile and gustatory senses in poetry. As Jon Anderson points out, “Cultural life does not take place in vacuum” (3) and human life is highly dependent on a context or a place, as things occur in a context that influences values, emotions, attitudes, celebrations, and activities.

Key words: Cultural Geography, Cultural Identity, Sensuality, Lacustrine Imagery, Symbolism, Phenomenology

Literature is a representation of the cultural geography and the society of the time. Kollam is renowned for freshwater lakes and

1 Assistant Professor of English, HHMSPB NSS College for Women, Thiruvananthapuram

varieties of fishes like Kanjirottu pearl spot², Kuzhali,³ Prachi and Kollam Parava⁴ etc. and other lake food varieties like Ashtamudi clam, Squid and Thevalakkara crab etc. Poetry of Kollam explicitly represents the different fish varieties from Ashtamudi lake as gustatory images through different contexts. In Unnuneeli Sandesam a sandesha kavya or message poem written in 1362 A.D, many shlokas are pictorial descriptions of Kollam and the poet describes the different varieties of fishes displayed for sale in the “muchanthikkal angadi” or the market in Kollam like “kola, moongan, choruku, kozhumeen, konchu, pambada, poomeen, chermeen, karimeen, koomen, azhila, njerimeen, palanandan” etc, available in abundance in the rivers and lakes of Kollam. Hence Unnuneeli Sandesam, cements the Ashtamudi lake as a source of food by detailing the different varieties of fishes.

In the poem “Ishtamudi Kayal”, written by the native poet Kurrepuzha Sreekumar, the poet cites the abundance of clam in the Ashtamudi lake as “the cloud of clam” clustered on the sides of the boat. The phrase “Kanjirottu kareemente thrikaliyattom”⁵, “mazha kholil pirakkunna narum kuzhali”⁶ are gustatory images that delineates the delicacies that water the mouths of the natives and the Ashtamudi lake as a mother image which feeds the natives with the tastiest king fish of the world. The poet considers the lake food

2. Kanjirottu Karemeen, the tastiest pearl spot in the world is a seafood delicacy of Kollam. This pearl spot is almost vegetarian and the world’s best planktons and mineral sand is in the Kanjirottu lake. GR. Indugopan cites it as the reason behind the unique taste to the Kanjirottu pearl spot in Twinkle Rossayum Pandrendu Kamukanmarum. V. Lakshmanan in his historical book Adunika Kollathinte Charithram cites Lord Curzon’s interest in Kanjirottu Karimeen even after leaving Kollam and his daughter reported that this pearl spot curry was sent to Delhi and then exported to Delhi.
3. “Kuzhali” is a tasty fresh water fish which was seen in abundance under the rotten coconut husk in the Ashtamudi lake, earlier, especially during the rainy season. Now a days it’s scarcely available and is in the verge of extinction due to pollution in lakes and due to the decline of coir industry.
4. Kollam Parava is a fish variety available in Kollam
5. The line suggests the dance like playful movement of the bright green pearl spot in abundance in sun light, when they come to the crystal-clear water top in a group
6. The line suggests the abundance of the fish “kuzhali” available in rainy season.

varieties of Ashtamudi lake as inevitable source behind the health and vitality of the natives and prepare them to find a means of living as , “those who are in search of a job ,who are born in your soft belly needs crab and clam to call slogans to fight” (185).

The poet later shares his memory in a lecture on the curiosity of people from different parts of Kerala to visit Kollam to taste the fresh water variety of fish mentioned in the poem like “Kuzhali”, which was abundantly available from Ashtamudi lake, in his childhood, especially during the rainy season .The unique taste of the fresh water fish “kuzhali” is also mentioned in the poem , “Oothakalam”, written by the native poet Bhaskaran Nair where he describes “Kuzhali” as a fish disgusting in sight but palatable for the tongue.

The poem “Oothakalam”, by the native poet Bhaskaran Nair describes the typical rustic scenes of Kollam, and the dependence of the natives in lakes and rivers to quench their hunger in the rainy season and the poverty and struggles of the villagers to make both ends meet and the unity and brotherhood of Kollam. The poet details the thrill and thrive of the natives of Kollam in harvesting the surging small fish varieties called “Ootha”, in rainy season and the appetizing taste combination of tapioca and bird pepper chutney mixed with coconut oil and the river fish curry which motivates the natives to overcome the hurdles in catching “ootha” in adverse climate with cane cage which needs much expertise and patience. The poet details the simple joys of the mass culture of the rustics of Kollam, by describing their preparations before going for fish harvesting like taking cane cage, arecanut leaf sheath, basket etc. They also remind one another to take matchbox,beedi, and arrack to amuse themselves while harvesting in the extreme cold weather and instruct the women to prepare both ground coconut paste and roasted coconut gravy in advance for making fish curry when they come back harvesting fish in abundance.The poem mentions the small fish varieties named “ootha” like “kuri, kari, kaithakora ,pallathi, vlanjil, kareemeen, vaha, mala” etc and showcases the fish harvesting during the monsoon season as a celebration for the natives.

Poetry mirrors the intricate connection of Ashtamudi lake with the cultural life of Kollam in different angles like food, livelihood, language, entertainment etc. Coir industry flourished in Kollam due to the availability of plenty of coconut husk, the raw material for coir manufacture and due to the presence of Ashtamudi lake, as it provides a medium for the rotting the coconut husk. *Unnuneeli Sandesham* cements coir manufacture as an indigenous profession of Kollam and mentions about the coir displayed in muchanthikkal angadi for sale. The poem showcases even the minute details of coir and coir products available in the “muchanthikkal angadi” or the market in Kollam through a picturesque description. “Rani”, is another poem written in the backdrop of coir manufacture in Ashtamudi lake by the native poet Thirunalloor Karunakaran. The poem foregrounds the lake as a means of living through the manufacture and transportation of coir. Coir manufacture was an indigenous profession of Kollam, and the natives once woke and slept by the sounds of the “coir ratts” and their life was highly bound to the climatic mood swings of the river. The poet explicitly states it in the preface of the poem as, “the shore will awake in the dawn itself and raise the magical music of human effort in the making of golden garlands from the rotten husk. The painful human heart impulses gets drenched in the flow of sound from the ratts” (Karunakaran 8). The poem abounds with the images related to the indigenous coir manufacture on the shores of Ashtamudi lake like “the ratts always singing the music of human effort”, the tune of tender hands beating the coconut husk”, “the boats carrying the Ashtamudi coir in roaring winds”, “making of mali⁷ with her friends on the shores” etc. The poem ends with the sudden demise of Nanu, a representative of the working class of Kollam, due to pneumonia, as he worked hard in extreme cold to build a thatch house to live together with Rani after their marriage. The lake is portrayed as a cultural landscape to which the life and dreams of the natives is highly depended on, either

7. “Mali” is a process of walking backwards with rolls of coir threads during the coir manufacture. It was once a common sight in different parts of Kollam, a land renowned for coir manufacture.

to flourish or to peril of on the shores which the poet states in the preface of the poem as, “The lake truly reflects our life especially at the time of land winds and monsoon .The lake will be in turbulence with the disturbance in our hearts.Waves will roar,break on the shores and jolted awake like our lives”(Karunakaran 8).

In the poem “Ishtamudi” penned by the native poet Kureepuzha Sreekumar, the lake teems with myriad forms of relationship with natives and showcases the indigenous occupation of Kollam like coir manufacture , fishing etc ,and evokes the memories of the working class through the thriving and thrilling occupational songs reverberating on the banks of the lake. The rotten smell of the coconut husk, the raw material for coir manufacture is an olfactory image which showcases the good old times of the indigenous coir manufacture on the banks of the lake and how the Ashtamudi lake becomes a part and parcel of the life of Kollam.The poem constructs the cultural identity of the natives through the phrase “charoo paroo”, a linguistic environment which shares the naive cultural expression of human effort and unity to ease the strain of their work. The phrase “charoo paroo” is an auditory image that echoes in the workplaces of Kollam as a token of brotherhood,cooperation and unity among the natives in the cultural landscape of Kollam and the poem showcases the identity construction in natives through language.

The poem portrays the Ashtamudi lake as a structural backdrop for the blooming of love between Nanu and Rani and the smell of “poo kaitha” and the snow laden shores of the lake at night set the ambiance of their love. The “poo kaitha” , a flower abundantly seen on the banks of the Ashtamudi lake with mesmerizing smell ,which evokes a romantic ambiance is also mentioned in *Unnuneeli Sandesam*. The line that describes Rani as a paragon of beauty like “From where ,from where did this lass got this sort of charm”(Karunakaran 11) , explicitly elicits the role of the lake in enhancing the beauty of the woman and in constructing the identity and aesthetic sense of the natives.

The poem ‘Rani’ showcases Ashtamudi lake as a backdrop of love when co -workers tease Rani the heroine, for breaking “mali”

when she gets excited by the sight of Nanu rowing his boat in the Ashtamudi lake. The poem portrays the lake as a beautiful woman with emotional turbulence and abounds with aspects of female sensuousness. The lakes and greenery of Kollam serves as a cultural backdrop of love and erotic dreams in the literature Kollam.

In “Ishtamudi Kayal” cherishes his memories of the Ashtamudi lake and addresses her intimately as “Ishtamudi”. The title “Ishtamudi” itself is a semiotic addressal of poet’s intimacy with the Ashtamudi lake and the poem abounds with lacustrine cultural semiotics in the course of unravelling the flow of poet’s life from childhood to youth. The Ashtamudi lake remains a fluid symbolic space in creating the identity of the natives through language, love, food, myth, and lake lores. The poem is in the form of a panegyric to Ashtamudi lake and the lake is personified as an erotic, gorgeous woman when he addresses the Ashtamudi lake as the woman who lies and spreads herself before him like a beautiful woman, the one who twists and turns with the rhythm of the tune of his shaft. The poem abounds with female sensuousness when the poet shares his mesmerising experience through a tactile image of entering the lap of the cool water of ‘sambrani kodi’ like a lover and the enthralling feel of experiencing the depth and beauty of the lake like a woman.

In the poem “Ishtamudi kayal” , Kureepuzha suggests an ecofeminist reading of the Ashtamudi lake “ with her eight braids like a woman beautifully plaits her hair together and manages the wind with hundred fingers, as one twists and spreads like a woman, as one dances with the tune of his shaft”. The poem abounds with fluid semiotics , as a signification addressed as “karumbi kotha”, as a woman who keeps folk songs on her lap to encourage the native workers, as a lover who lures the poet hiding the depth of her unseen beauty, as a maternal trope feeding the natives with nutritious food to raise slogans for their struggle and survival, and to forgive the mischiefs of her disobedient children with maternal affection, as a powerful deity to protect the natives and to preserve the deserted islands from the hooligans .

“Rani” foregrounds the Ashtamudi lake as a maiden who becomes turbulent, as if tainted, when the wind touches her green corsage. The beautiful heroine Rani is addressed as “river goddess” , when

she travels in a boat through the lake, is a reflection of river image constructed as a deity, the collective unconscious of the natives. As Carl Jung explained religion as a manifestation of the collective consciousness, the poem extends the possibility of comparing the chaste and beautiful heroine Rani to a river goddess in the mind of her lover and the natives. The poem mirrors the human dependence on Nature, and the awe and fear created in the natives when the water becomes turbulent by the tidal waves. The turbid and turbulent river accompanied by the roaring wind disturbs the normalcy of the life of the natives like the uncontrolled wrath of an angry deity.

The poem 'Rani' showcases Ashtamudi lake as a backdrop of love when co-workers tease Rani the heroine, for breaking "mali", when she gets excited by the sight of Nanu rowing his boat in the Ashtamudi lake. The poem portrays the lake as a beautiful woman with emotional turbulence and abounds with aspects of female sensuousness. The Ashtamudi lake and the greenery on its banks serves as a cultural backdrop of love and erotic dreams in the poetry of Kollam.

The Ashtamudi lake serves as a symbolic network of incessant fluvial life images, as something inseparable from the life of the natives, as something not only decorates their public space but also communicates in their private thoughts. Casey explains ... "place is regarded as constitutive of one's sense of self... The relationship between self and place is not just one of reciprocal influence ... but also more radically, of constitutive ingredients each is essential to the being of the other. In effect there is no place without self and no self without place" (684).

The poem also focuses on the human issues in the social life on the banks such as financial decline, agricultural crisis, unemployment, anti-social activities, hooliganism, and atrocities against women faced by the natives of Kollam. "Culture is therefore the constituted amalgam of human activity. Culture is what humans do" (Jon Anderson 3). The poem portrays the lake as a cultural landscape which serves as a mother, bread giver, lover and an inspiration for the natives, and intricately connected as a continuum of their life and remains as an abstract cultural imprint in the psyche of the natives. As Jon Anderson quotes Cresswell who rightly describes

this as “the fish don’t talk about the water; in normal life we are often like the fish in that we don’t talk about our geographical context” (1). As water attains different shapes in different containers the river remains a fluid space for the natives that attains different identity in different cultures.

Kollam was a renowned centre of trade and commerce as there is a harbour to transport goods and machinery. Thirunallor Karunakaran’s poem titled “Kollam” hails the glory of Kollam harbour, where so many ships with the flags of the East and the West come in line as a feast for the eye. The poem gives a picturesque image of the fleets of ship which flows to rest on the shore passing Neendakara Azhi. The poet portrays Kollam as the place pampered and fostered by Arabian sea and addresses her as “the bosom friend of Ashtamudi lake” (Karunakaran 5).

“Mayoora Sandesham”, mirrors how water serves as a mode of transport for the natives and how water entertains the cultural life of Kollam through the peacock’s description of its boat journey. The messenger peacock travels by water and gets informed that when he reaches Kollam, he would be happy by the sight of the happy Lords and Ladies. Ulloor describes that mesmerizing scene in his translation of Mayoora Sandesham entitled, “The Peacock Messenger” as “Lords of the land ,gaily pass along , the boatmen singing many a merry song ; And on the deck the Saheb may be found , His eyes repasting on the scenes around the wide spread waters” in Kollam and ensures the peacock that “...to thee this lake side scene must doubtless pleasing be” (Ulloor 260). “Mayoora sandesham” portrays Kollam as a land that surpasses the capital city with its facilities, of which the poet mentions ‘Kollam’, as a land of water bodies, as “water for bath which ever soothes the mind” (261). Water bodies of Kollam especially Ashtamudi lake remains a powerful cultural motif of entertainment, transport and beauty in poetry.

The poem “Ashtamudi” written by the native poet ONV showcases the picturesque cultural images of day to day activities of the people residing on the banks like transportation of vegetables and grocery in “kevu vallam”⁸ and fishing in small boats, the greenery made by

8. Kevu vallam, or Charakku vallam in native language is a large vessel used for transporting cargoes. This vessel is covered by thatched roof in order to protect the cargo from sun, rain and wind.

“malar kaitha” and coconut trees surrounding the lake etc which entertains the poet in his boat journey through Ashtamudi and parades the Ashtamudi lake as a fluvial presence in the cultural life of the natives. The poem abounds with cultural images experienced by the poet as a native of Kollam. As Hyden says “Place is one of the trickiest words in the English language, a suitcase so overfilled that one can never shut the lid” (112).

The Ashtamudi lake and the social life around it form the mainstay of the cultural landscape in the poem “Ishtamudi kayal”. The poem mentions the location with important settlements around the lake such as Neendakara, Vellimon, Perumon, Kadavoor, and Kanjiroodu etc. The poem abounds with aesthetically rich lacustrine poetic images expressing various aspects of the lake which moulds the creativity of the native poets and artists. The temporal aspects pertaining to the landscape and the colour change in the lake like the moodswings of a woman are displayed as per the seasons, and time such as monsoon, summer and noon and sunset and is a visual image that caters to the creativity in the colour combination of the famous painter like Jayapalan and other poets.

Poetry of Kollam echoes the many voices of Ashtamudi lake, the individual drops of water mirrors strong cultural motifs of love, motherhood, femininity, belief and Nature and showcase the rivers and lakes of Kollam as a symbolic network of sociality, and ecological dependence of the natives in myriad forms. The cultural images of Ashtamudi in the poetry of Kollam murmurs the pangs and pathos of the natives, the happy tunes of the social vibes, the secret whispers of the lover and the beloved, the silent oozing of the maternal love, the sacred chanting of beliefs and myths, sometimes in the vernacular and sometimes in a decorum suitable for the locale and society and sometimes a diction intelligible to the inhabitants and sometimes an outcry of the public for a common cause.

The poetry of Kollam brims with poetic images of Ashtamudi as a recurring presence that constructs the identity of the natives, as well as the identity of the lake itself, as a female, as a mother, as a deity, as a lover, as a maiden as Nature etc. The Ashtamudi lake is foregrounded as a fluid space of cultural identity with a panoramic view of lacustrine imagery in the poetry of Kollam. The lake, like a

charming woman, plaits her beautiful hair, shakes her eight braids, with boats harvesting fishes like a water bird, transporting people and vegetables becomes a part and parcel of human life with fluidity and transmutability. The lake imagery in the poems suggest a symbolic network of human dependency on river like as a source of food , as a mode of transport ,as a female who shapes the aesthetics of the natives etc.As Casey points out , “Places begin to possess us ...insinuating themselves into our lives”(199).The poetry of Kollam reflects the lake as a cultural text to portray the concepts of love, sexuality ,dreams and means of living of the natives.As Bolter cited in Thomashow , “We write the culture in which we live” (184).

Works Cited

- Casey,E. *Remembering a Phenomenological Study*.Indiana U P, 1996.
 Jon Anderson. *Understanding Cultural Geography: Places and Traces*,
 Routledge, 2010.
 Hayden,D.*Urban Landscape History:The Sense of Place and the Politics of
 Space*. Edited by In Groth,P and Bressi,T , YaYale P, 1997. Pp. 11 -33.
 Karunakaran, Thirunalloor. *Rani*. SPCS, 2015, pp 11.
 ... “Kollam”,*Greeshma Sandhyakal*.SPCS,2014.
 Kunjan Pillai, Sooranattu. *Unnuneeli Sandesham*. Kerala Bhasha Institute,
 1996.
 Kurup,ONV. “Ashtamudi.” *ONV yude Kavithakal*. DC Books,2008.
 Lakshmanan, V. Kollathinte Adunikka Charithram,1996,Kollam Adunika
 Prakasana Samithi,Page 408.
 Nair,Bhaskaran P. “Oothakalam.” *Kudayum Njaanum*. Ulloor Samskarika
 Vedi, 2023, pp.10.
 Sreekumar, Kureepuzha. “ Ishtamudi Kayal.” *Kureepuzha Sreekumarinte
 Kavithakal*. DC Books, 2021, pp.182 -185.
 Valiya KoiThampuram, Kerala Varma. *MayooraSandesham*. Translated by
 Ulloor, St .Joseph Press,1978 , pp 260.
 Yung, Carl. “ The Structure of the Unconscious”.The Collected Works, 1916.

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series Vol. XVI. Book I-IV

January - December 2024

ISSN 0975-4067

Printed and published by: Dr.C.S.Sasikumar, Secretary, Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram, for Sanskrit Research Foundation,